

Pneumonia Detection and Classification using Vision Transformer from Pneumonia MNIST Dataset

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Abstract: Pneumonia is a severe lung infection requiring quick diagnosis to avoid serious complications. Chest X-rays are the most common and reliable diagnostic tools. In healthcare, several deep learning predictive algorithms have been created to streamline and improve the accuracy of diagnoses. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have automated and improved the accuracy of image classification for pneumonia diagnoses. Having said that, medical image processing involves identifying long-range and complex dependencies within images. This is problematic because mild and subtle signs of pneumonia would be overlooked. Vision Transformer (ViT) can analyze long-range and complex dependencies within images. ViT is a highly scalable and advanced model for image classification. ViT divides an image into smaller sections and uses Multi-Head Self-Attention to form and analyze global context, determining relationships within each section and focusing on pairwise relationships. Research and findings within this paper established that ViT architecture is better than CNN deep learning models. MedMNISTv2 collection contains the PneumoniaMNIST dataset, the dataset most commonly used for pneumonia image classification. The experiment results demonstrated that the performance of CNN and ViT models, and the Google ViT architecture with novel image augmentation, Adam optimization, learning warmup, and decay, achieved state-of-the-art accuracy of 99.96% in the training phase and 93.75% in the testing phase. These results indicate that ViT models outperform CNN models on the Pneumonia MNIST dataset. These results can lead to improvements, especially in the provision of diagnostic support to aid radiologists and clinicians in effective decision-making. This technology will be especially useful in low-resource settings where radiologists and well-furnished clinics are scarce.

Keywords – Multi-head Attention, Vision Transformer, Deep Learning, Pneumonia classification, MedMNISTv2

I. INTRODUCTION

Pneumonia occurs when an infection causes inflammation of the alveoli in one or both lungs. The air sacs may fill with fluid or pus, resulting in difficulty breathing, coughing, and impaired oxygen exchange. Several people recover fully with the right vaccination and early treatment. Good hygiene and medical care help keep this infection from becoming deadly. The World Health Organization (WHO) [1] said that the 2.5 million deaths, which include 740,000 children under the age of five, 14% of global deaths of children, children with weak immune systems, and children are the most vulnerable population. The highest burden of this disease lies in the poorer regions, specifically South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. India carries a significant burden of pneumonia, accounting for 23% of the global burden of pneumonia and 23% of the global under-5 mortality.

Pneumonia is particularly prevalent in India, with research from Johns Hopkins University and the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) [2] estimating the country has tens of millions of annual cases. High incidences can also be attributed to poor nutrition, inadequate healthcare, limited vaccination, and poor air quality. Even with national vaccination drives and awareness programs, pneumonia continues to be one of the most common causes of disease and death in India and the world.

Among various options, chest X-rays stand out as the most efficient and dependable technique for identifying pneumonia. X-rays provide enough information for both the physician and the radiologist to establish a diagnosis, as well as to identify lung infections and inflammation. Figure 1 illustrates the various presentations of pneumonia in X-

rays, as well as a comparison to normal lung X-rays. The X-ray shows the lung formations and outlines the portions that contain fluid, infections, or bones. The portions that are denser are whiter or grayish in color, making it easier to identify pneumonia as healthy lung tissue. The X-ray interpretations are complex and time-consuming, and the results can vary greatly from one radiologist to another. There are also challenges in diagnosing even the simplest and common cases of pneumonia. The physical examination, along with a standard chest X-ray, must precede a conclusive diagnosis while taking into account expert radiology. For healthcare providers, especially in rural and developing regions, the absence of X-ray examination coupled with the vague pneumonia indicators can become a real challenge. There is no doubt that the early diagnosis and treatment of a medical condition can dramatically improve the prognosis. The use of artificial intelligence, especially deep learning, CNNs, and ViTs for medical image analysis far surpasses the results of traditional methods. This prompted the current study to focus on developing pneumonia classification models based on CNNs and ViTs.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [3][4] have significantly advanced image classification. A neural network comprises sequential layers: convolutional, pooling, fully connected layers, and a classification layer. In image analytical tasks, models based on CNNs such as VGG16[5], Xception[6], ResNet[7], and EfficientNet[8] have excelled. Apart from EfficientNet, all other models have ranked highly in image classification tasks, and are one of the most cited. Apart from EfficientNet, all other models have ranked highly in image classification tasks, and are one of the most cited. Models based on CNNs have also excelled in classification of medical images and other healthcare applications. However, these models demanded even more preprocessing and standardization of the data for dependable and more generalizable outcomes. The CNN community has countered these deficiencies with improvements such as the integration of attention mechanisms [9][10]. Attention, a deep learning trend, has remarkably improved performance in several computer vision tasks and proposed CNN improvements due to the focus on enhanced global context and non-local modeling. Attention mechanisms in CNN frameworks enable better global context capturing and enhanced focus on each channel of the input feature maps[11]. Nevertheless, advanced attention mechanisms are computationally expensive, and the time complexity grows quadratically with the input dimensions.

Over the last few years, several Transform architecture variations have emerged. From machine translation to text classification, question answering, and text summarization, these architectures have proven invaluable to the completion of a variety of NLP tasks [12]. Their novelty is not lost, and they have revolutionized deep learning as a whole. Self-attention mechanisms, the fundamental building block of a transformer, allow the capture of long-range dependencies and symmetries present within the data. This has expanded the range of tasks where transformers can be used, such as computer vision tasks and image classification, image segmentation, image super-resolution[13], and object recognition. Vision Transformers draw from the expansive architectural capabilities of transformers to solve computer vision problems. For advanced visual data (e.g. medical imagery), transformers can replace CNNs. It is because of transformers' extensive pre-training, variable-length sequence tolerance, and multitasking ability that they are preferred in many tasks over CNNs. This is why the encoder goes through repeated transformations and reinforcement. The encoder block captures global image features and the semantic relationships embedded in visual data. The transformer encoder consists of Multi-Head Self-Attention (MHSA) and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) layers. Among these building blocks, MHSA captures the global characteristics from the embeddings. This explains why ViTs and their variants are the dominant models in medical image analysis, achieving state-of-the-art performance.

However, CNNs cannot encode the position and orientation of objects. Because CNNs recognize images as clusters of pixels arranged in different patterns, they do not treat them as components present in the image. Hence, ViTs have been proposed to overcome the limitations of CNNs in capturing long-range dependencies and global context. Based on this, ViTs can bring benefits to the pneumonia classification problem. This study provides an analysis and performance evaluation of the vision transformer and CNN models using the PneumoniaMNIST dataset. It develops a ViT model that automatically classifies X-ray images as pneumonia-positive or pneumonia-negative. Unlike traditional CNN models, this is a much more efficient and accurate approach. For this, the ViT variants—custom ViT, MAE ViT, DeiTViT, and Google ViT—are trained and compared with four CNN models: a custom CNN, EfficientNetB3, VGG16m, and Exception. The results underscore that a transformer-based model significantly outperforms CNN-based models, particularly on the PneumoniaMNIST dataset.

II. RELATED WORK

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are the default choice for vision tasks. They are designed with multiple convolutional layers, where different filters are used to detect local features. CNNs automatically learn features at different spatial hierarchies from raw input data. This ability makes CNNs effective in identifying patterns, anomalies, and disease markers in various medical images. Also, the classification of medical images relies on the ability to capture intricate structures and local dependencies. Thus, the development of automated, precise, and scalable medical image analysis hinges on the functionality of CNNs. A proficient hybrid CNN-Transformer model [14] has been proposed, which aims to merge the locality of CNNs with the global connectivity of Vision Transformers (ViTs). They integrated the convolution operation with the standard self-attention mechanism to solve the computational burden. They integrated self-attention, which adds quadratic complexity, and convolution. Their method alleviates the quadratic bottleneck and computational sluggishness of the basic self-attention framework by introducing a novel convolutional attention mechanism that rapidly converges across multiple information channels. They exhibited good robustness and generalization with a reduced computational burden. The hybrid model, in theory, retained ViT's exceptional performance while alleviating its quadratic computational cost.

Nevertheless, ViT layers are inflexible, costly, and computationally intensive because CNNs have an information bottleneck that restricts feature transfer. The main issue deals with deploying the model in the real world efficiently and at scale. Another hybrid model was designed to classify pneumonia in X-ray images [15]. This model showed considerable promise, but it was not evaluated on multi-resolution or diverse real-world datasets. The Vision Transformer model [16], was designed to classify images as pneumonia-positive or not and extract feature maps. This work benchmarked ViT and CNN models against MobileNetV2, VGG16, and ResNet50 and concluded that ViT models outperform CNN models. It lacks generalization, computational efficiency, and has a performance ceiling on imbalanced datasets. The work on pneumonia diagnosis [17] uses a Kaggle dataset on X-ray images and employs a Vision Transformer model. This work demonstrates that ViT models capture global context, understand spatial relations, and perform better across multiple X-ray resolutions. This work also incorporates more advanced metrics for evaluating deep learning models for pneumonia detection on X-rays, namely accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity. A hybrid deep learning model [18] was also proposed, where CNNs are fused with modified Swin Transformer [19] blocks.

CNN layers detect the basic features and local patterns of the X-ray images. The modified Swin Transformer [20] blocks harness the concept of long-range dependencies to build global context. The global context is preserved using a window-based self-attention. The proposed study also uses the same pre-processing techniques to improve image features. Furthermore, to ensure sufficient training samples for the model, the proposed study employs data augmentation. The proposed architecture has shown remarkable performance on an unseen dataset, exceeding that of a baseline CNN model. Wang Wenhai et al.[20] designed the Pyramid Vision Transformer (PVT) as a multi-stage structure, which enhances performance on both image classification and dense prediction tasks. Liu Ze et al.[21] developed the Swin Transformer, which optimized the attention mechanism by implementing a window-based self-attention system to enhance scalability and efficiency for high-resolution inputs.

While Transformers have shown encouraging results for basic vision tasks, their application in medical imaging is still in its infancy. Most studies focusing on smaller, niche datasets like PneumoniaMNIST do not provide adequate comparisons between different Transformer models (ViT, MAE, DeiT, and Google ViT) and legacy CNN architectures (VGG16, EfficientNet-B3, and Xception). The scarcity of research on ViT and pneumonia is particularly troubling, considering how pneumonia, especially during COVID-19, poses one of the most pressing global health challenges. For this reason, studying the application of ViT to pneumonia is essential, and this work aims to fill part of that void. Moreover, this research presents an integrated performance analysis of the PneumoniaMNIST dataset [22], tailored for pneumonia detection in chest X-rays. This analysis contributes to the understanding of medical image classification by comparing the performance and feature representation capabilities of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Vision Transformer (ViT) models. Going forward, it will continue this research and strive to achieve results that surpass traditional methods.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this study, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Vision Transformers (ViTs) are used to classify chest X-ray images as Normal or Pneumonia. Primary modeling strategies involve both traditional CNNs and transformers.

A. Dataset Description

For this research, the PneumoniaMNIST dataset, which is part of the MedMNISTv2 collection [22], is used. It is an open-access dataset tailored for the classification of medical images. In particular, the dataset is oriented towards classifying cases of pneumonia. It is split into two categories: images of patients with pneumonia, and images of patients whose condition appears normal.

The PneumoniaMNIST dataset comprises 5,856 chest X-ray images, which are used for binary classification of pneumonia (pneumonia vs. normal chest). The dataset is partitioned into a training, validation, and testing set. The training set contains 4,700 images, 524 are in the validation set, and the testing set includes 624 images. All the images are in grayscale, and each one is 28×28 pixels. In order to be compatible with the baseline ViT architecture, images are upscaled to 224×224 pixels. Sample X-ray images from the dataset are shown in Figure 1. The images also undergo preprocessing to improve model performance and generalization. First, quality-improving denoising and normalization are performed. This step is critical for alleviating the weak performance of deep learning models. Second, data augmentation is performed again after normalization, but prior to model training. Applied data augmentation includes rotation, flipping, and brightness adjustments.

Figure 1: Sample images from the PneumoniaMNIST dataset

B. Custom CNN Model

In this study, a customized Convolutional Neural Network (CCNN) is used. This model contains multiple layers, which progressively process and simplify the input image. The CNN model uses two functions to extract the localization features and reduce the dimensions of the data. Convolution and pooling functions are the main components of a CNN. These functions are repeatedly utilized throughout the network, in order to extract pertinent features from the image, to classify it. The standard CNN architecture for image classification is illustrated in Figure 2. The functions are called layers in the network, and the convolution layers use different filters for the extraction of progressively more abstract features, while the pooling layers reduce the dimensions of the data. To control overfitting, dropout layers are used, and to incorporate non-linearity, activation functions are used. Network complexity is defined by the number of filters and layers, and features are classified after flattening them and passing them through a fully connected neural network. The custom CNN model is constructed and trained on the PneumoniaMNIST dataset.

The Custom CNN model has several convolutional layers configured with ReLU activations, followed by batch normalization, a max pooling layer, and includes a dropout layer. The CCNN model has several dropout layers and a sigmoid layer for binary classification. This model has several customization options. Each layer is configured with a unique set of filters of varied sizes to allow the model to use higher parameters for optimization.

Figure 2: Standard CNN Architecture for image classification

C. Pre-trained CNN Models

For pneumonia classification, this study utilized three pre-trained deep convolutional neural networks: VGG16, Xception, and EfficientNet-B3. These networks serve as the backbone for multiple neural networks that can classify and segment medical images. For local feature extraction and image classification, VGG16 [5] utilizes 3×3 convolutions and achieves 13 convolutional layers and three fully connected layers. VGG16 is a baseline architecture as it exhibits performance levels and complexity that are comparable to those of more advanced neural networks. Xception[6] is an Inception variant that uses depth-wise separable convolutions to reduce parameters through a pointwise convolution (1×1 convolution). In contrast to CNNs, this model significantly lowers computational costs and the number of parameters. EfficientNet-B3 [8] utilizes compound scaling to achieve the mobile convolutional neural network model. In a balanced manner, EfficientNet-B3 scales depth, width, and input resolution. It is prevalent across multiple domains for image classification, such as medical image classification, product recognition, and agriculture. In this study, we adjusted pre-trained models VGG16, Xception, and EfficientNet-B3 for pneumonia classification, obtaining satisfactory results. These models represent the lowest complexity in terms of resource and memory consumption and serve as pre-training models to extract deep feature representations from medical images. These three add interpretability, computational constraints, and robustness to medical image classification.

D. Vision Transformer (ViT) Models

Vision Transformer is a powerful sequence model for computer vision. It divides an image into a sequence of patches, much as words are handled in natural language processing. Figure 3 presents the standard ViT architecture for image classification. Each patch is flattened and projected into a sequence of patch embeddings. Since transformers are order-agnostic, ViTs add learnable positional embeddings to each image patch to retain spatial information. Furthermore, a classification token is added to the patch embedding sequence. Several transformer encoder layers are then used to process this entire sequence. Each encoder layer consists of feedforward neural network sub-layers and Multi-Head Self-Attention (MHSA) mechanisms. These sub-layers collaborate to identify intricate patterns in the data, which helps the model produce precise classification predictions. The Masked Autoencoder (MAE), the Data-efficient Image Transformer (DeiT), and Google's initial ViT Base model were the three pre-trained ViT models that were refined in the second method. Transfer learning techniques were used to train these models on the PneumoniaMNIST dataset, after they had been initialised using pre-trained weights. Similar to the custom model, these pre-trained versions processed the visual data using the original transformer encoder framework and positional embeddings.

Every 224×224 input image was separated into 16×16 non-overlapping patches, resulting in a total of (224*224)/16 patches. Using a trainable linear layer, each patch was flattened and projected to a fixed-length embedding vector. Positional encodings (*Epos*) were added to the embeddings to maintain spatial order. Equation 1 represents the mathematical notation of the input image.

$$X = [x_{class}, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n] + E_{pos} \quad (1)$$

where *xclass* is a special classification token and *x1, x2, ..., xn* are the patch embeddings. These inputs were then processed through transformer encoder layers.

Figure 3: Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture

IV. EXPERIMENT

A. Experiment Setup and Data Preprocessing

In regard to decreasing overfitting and generalization, various data augmentation techniques were employed on the PneumoniaMNIST dataset. These techniques were horizontal random image flipping, rotation, and zooming. To be compatible with pretrained models, the MNIST dataset was modified to use bigger grayscale images. The original images, which were 28×28 pixel grayscale images, had to be expanded to 224×224 pixel images. To keep the images manageable, the pixel values were set to a normal range of 0 to 1. For the assessment of the model to be functional in all stages, split the dataset into three subsets of 70%-training, 10%-validation, and 20%-testing.

B. Model Training

Two types of models were trained and assessed in this study. CNN-based models and Vision Transformer (ViT) based models. Basic convolutional and pooling layers were used to create a single unique model for the CNN-based method [23]. Furthermore, using the pneumonia dataset, three pre-trained models, VGG16 [5], EfficientNetB3 [8], and Xception[6] were trained. Every CNN model employed the Adam optimizer [24], a learning rate of 0.0001, and the categorical cross-entropy loss function. To avoid overfitting, each model was trained for 10 epochs with early stopping, and a batch size of 16 was used.

A custom Vision Transformer (ViT) model was developed in Keras for the Vision Transformer-based category, splitting input images into 16×16 -pixel patches. Positional encodings were incorporated to preserve spatial information, and multiple Transformer encoder layers with multi-head self-attention [25] were used. In addition to the custom ViT, three pre-trained transformer models, such as ViT Base (google/vit-base-patch16-224), DeiT-Tiny (facebook/deit-tiny-patch16-224), and MAE (facebook/vit-mae-base), were fine-tuned through transfer learning. All ViT models were trained with the Adam optimizer using sparse categorical cross-entropy loss, a learning rate of 0.0001, and consistent batch size and epoch settings as the CNN models.

V. RESULT

In this study, multiple models were evaluated for pneumonia detection using the PneumoniaMNIST dataset. Under the CNN-based category, we first trained a custom CNN model explicitly designed for this binary classification task. Additionally, three widely used pre-trained convolutional models, VGG16, EfficientNetB3, and Xception, were fine-tuned for comparison. Among these, the Xception model achieved the highest test accuracy of 92.65%, followed by EfficientNetB3 with 90.95% and VGG16 with 87.60%. Despite its relative simplicity, the custom CNN model managed to record a reasonable accuracy of 85.68%, a proof of its capability for minor applications.

Two types of models were tested for the Vision Transformer: custom and pretrained. Starting from scratch, building the custom ViT model with Keras was encouraging as it recorded a test accuracy of 83.80%. In addition, three recently enhanced pretrained transformer models were adapted to fine-tune: ViT Base (google/ViT-base-patch16-224), DeiT Tiny (facebook/DeiT-tiny-patch16-224), and MAE (facebook/vit-mae-base). ViT-Base fine-tuner offered the best test accuracy (93.75%) followed by both DeiT and MAE at 93.27%. The accuracy recorded by fine-tuned Vision Transformers, even for small medical imaging datasets (PneumoniaMNIST), consolidates the Vision Transformers pre-training's additional value. During training of the CNN and ViT models, the training and validation accuracy were recorded and plotted (refer to Figures 12-19). From these figures, it can be seen that all models demonstrate a trend of loss reduction and stability, indicating the models likely reached convergence quickly. No overfitting was observed during training.

In evaluating the proposed models for the PneumoniaMNIST dataset, the performance metrics included accuracy, precision, recall, and the F1 score. These metrics normalize the performance of the classification models, including the quantification of true positives and true negatives. Additionally, these metrics take into account the dataset imbalances. In binary classification, the positive sample is identified as Pneumonia and the negative sample as normal. Each predicted binary output has four possible designations. They include true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP), and false negative (FN). A true positive is a predicted Pneumonia case that was correct, a true negative is a correct predicted case of normal, a false positive is a case of normal predicted to be Pneumonia, and a false negative is a case of Pneumonia predicted to be normal. The number of TP, TN, FP, and FN for a specific predicted output is accounted for in a 2×2 confusion matrix.

Among the performance metrics, accuracy is the simplest to compute. It is the total number of correctly classified X-rays, both Pneumonia and normal, out of the total instances. Equation 2 shows the formula to compute

accuracy. A dataset can also have high accuracy, but it is misleading, especially when the dataset is imbalanced. Real-time applications, such as medical image classification, often present the problem of unbalanced datasets. Evaluating classification performance solely with accuracy can be misleading and insufficient. This is the case with medical diagnostics, particularly pneumonia classification from X-rays. False negatives can be more dangerous in healthcare. Therefore, when measuring the performance of classification models, other metrics such as precision, recall, and the F1-score need to be considered.

$$Accuracy(Acc) = \frac{(TP+TN)}{(TP+TN+FP+FN)} \quad (2)$$

Precision is the rate of positive accuracy. It is the number of correct positive predictions in the total actual predictions classified as positive and is given in Equation 3.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{(TP+FP)} \quad (3)$$

Recall, also known as the true positive rate, is the percentage of true positives the model predicts. More formally, it is the score of true positive predictions to the total instances of the positive class. It gauges the model's ability to capture every actual Pneumonia case. Equation 4 defines recall in mathematical terms. A high value in recall means the model does not frequently miss actual Pneumonia cases.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{(TP+FN)} \quad (4)$$

The F1-score considers false negatives and false positives. It measures how well the model predicts. It is calculated as twice the proportion of precision to recall, then divided by the sum of precision and recall. The equation displays the F1-score.

$$F1\ Score = 2 \times \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (5)$$

Now, Vision Transformers (ViTs) are most preferred for task performance pinnacles compared to convolutional neural networks (CNN) for medical image classification. This performance study notes consistency when comparing ViT to CNN in the performance metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Performance can be attributed to architectural designs. The pretrained ViT (Google) model reached a classification test accuracy of 93.75% and training accuracy of 99.96%. The model also registered test performance metrics for precision, recall, and F1-score. Performance consistency demonstrates reliability in medical image classification. An additional observation highlights convergence stability in training where fine-tuning is done. Compared to CNNs, ViT pretrained and fine-tuned models converge with more stability and faster completion. This feature is because ViT models are pretrained and designed to operate without relying on spatial hierarchies.

For CNNs, it is still necessary to learn the spatial hierarchies and the information. This study marks the first steps towards understanding the potential Vision Transformer has in the progression of medical image classification. Models that were pretrained on large-scale datasets, specifically ImageNet, exhibited more robust transfer learning potential. This contributes to the overall ability to perform more efficiently in low-data environments. This is more beneficial within medical imaging, considering the lack of datasets that have been annotated by specialists. The classification results from our model evaluations and comparisons are provided in Tables 1 and 2. As seen in the tables, the Google ViT model that has been pre-trained attained the most accuracy. This included (and most notably) precision, recall, and the F1 Score. Therefore, the pre-trained ViT model exemplifies outstanding performance metrics and generalization capability. They are also proficient in learning in scenarios where there is limited labeled data.

Figure 4: Confusion Matrix of CNN

Figure 7: Confusion Matrix of Xception

Figure 5: Confusion Matrix of Efficient-B3

Figure 8: Confusion Matrix of ViT

Figure 6: Confusion Matrix of VGG16

Figure 9: Confusion Matrix of MAE ViT

Figure 10: Confusion Matrix of Google ViT

Figure 11: Confusion Matrix of DeiT ViT

Table 1: Training and Testing Accuracies

Model Category	Model Name	Trainin g Accuracy (%)	Testing Accuracy (%)
CNN (Custom)	Custom	95.7	85.
CNN (Pretrained)	EfficientNe tB3	93.4	90.
		5	95

	VGG16	3	88.7	87.
	Xception	3	97.9	92.
ViT (Custom)	Custom ViT	6	96.7	83.
ViT (Pretrained)	MAE ViT	3	99.8	93.
	DeiT-Tiny	6	99.9	93.
	Google ViT	6	99.9	93.

Table 1. Precision, Recall, and F1 Score

Model	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 Score (%)
Custom CNN	89.23	79.67	81.90
EfficientNetB3	92.57	89.76	90.78
VGG16	86.45	85.34	86.55
Xception	92.67	85.58	87.86
Custom ViT	90.98	91.01	89.96
DeiT-Tiny (Facebook)	90.34	91.56	90.67
ViT-MAE Base (Facebook)	90.98	91.67	90.55
ViT Base (Google)	93.45	94.88	91.43

Figure 12: Accuracy curve of CNN

Figure 16: Accuracy curve of Custom ViT

ViT

Figure 13: Accuracy curve of EfficientNet-B3

Figure 14: Accuracy curve of VGG16

Figure 15: Accuracy curve of Xception

Figure 17: Accuracy curve of MAE ViT

Figure 18: Accuracy curve of DeiTViT

Figure 19: Accuracy curve of Google ViT

VI. DISCUSSION

This paper encompasses a detailed comparative assessment of CNN and ViT models, focusing on both custom and pre-trained versions. The evaluation of models on the PneumoniaMNIST dataset focused on classifying, calculating precision, recall, F1-score, and generalization. The testing results are shown in the confusion matrices provided in Figures 4 to 11. It is evident that CNN approaches, more so pre-trained CNN models, are superior in performance. The pre-trained CNN models showed heightened accuracy and ascertainment. The training and validation accuracy of the models selected for this study are depicted in Figures 12 to 19. These models adopt large-scale, pre-trained weights. This weight and resource ‘free’ distribution is a working hypothesis considering its marked influence on performance for the research focused on medical image classification. Even though the custom CNN model lagged a touch, it still produced competitive results. A custom CNN model was also a functional constituent feature extractor for medical image classification. Indeed, inferior performance was shown by the pre-trained ViT-based models as opposed to the custom ViT models, suggesting that custom models are less beneficial. The pre-trained models received benefits relative to large-dataset training. The training pre-dates the model to more significant inductive biases and more advanced generalization. The results showed that pre-trained models of both CNN and transfer-based architectures in model construction completed SOTA performance in medical image classification, alongside reduced training from scratch.

Based on an all-encompassing performance evaluation, Vision transformers ranked slightly higher than CNN and ViT-based models in executing classification tasks with constrained training data. While CNNs achieved their maximal performance relatively early during training, ViTs consistently showed performance enhancement through each epoch. This indicates that the self-attention mechanism in ViTs allows them to capture the broader context, and thus, they gain more from extended training periods and adjustments.

Notably, CNNs seem to outperform ViTs while performing fewer epochs, especially in low-resource contexts, as CNNs are less resource-intensive. The pre-training/fine-tuning phases did show ViT models taking more epochs to get to tempered optimum accuracy and, in the end, accuracy rivaled or surpassed all competitors. The highest performance in the sample was the pre-trained vision transformer with the Xception backbone. This seems to encourage the merging of transformer models with deep pretrained convolutional backbones. This finding

corroborates previous studies, like that of Dosovitskiy et al[25], where vision transformers have the upper hand with larger datasets. It is worth saying that on the smaller PneumoniaMNIST dataset, vision transformers, pre-trained, come close to outperforming CNNs. This points to transfer learning being a considerable performance influence, irrespective of the underlying architecture. In this study, while pretrained vision transformer models proved the most efficient, it is clear to see that both type of models have apparent strengths.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study used the PneumoniaMNIST dataset from the MedMNIST collection to assess and compare the performance of custom and pretrained models of CNN and ViT architectures for medical image classification. TensorFlow and the Keras library were used for the implementation of all models. Results across all models demonstrate that the pretrained ViT models markedly attained better classification accuracy, and pre-analytical metrics (precision, recall, and F1-score). In order to reduce noise and background details, scarcity of data, and for normalization purposes, all models underwent pre-processing and data augmentation, which were applied prior to training the models. In conclusion, pre-trained ViT models are more advanced compared to custom CNNs, pre-trained CNNs, and custom ViT models. The CNN models did exhibit strong, stable performance; however, the ViT models, during training, were much more progressive. Although the PneumoniaMNIST dataset, when compared to general image datasets, is small, the ViT models still produced strong results and generalized well. The results of this study demonstrated that pretrained ViTs are a viable CNN alternative for medical image classification. It is equally important to note the necessity to work on more extensive and varied datasets of medical images.

The future direction and plans to extend this study are to use larger and multi-regional datasets to evaluate robustness and generalizability in terms of data quality and demographic diversity. The ensemble and the hybrid deep learning architectures must be compared. Also, explore novel data augmentation techniques and alternatives for pre-trained learning methods. In addition, exploring the interpretability of the results produced by the CNN and the ViT remains a considerable challenge in medical image analysis

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